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Role of Pakistan in India-China Relations

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Abstract In the aftermath of 1962 war between India and China, the complex relationship between two Asian rivals has always one constant factor and that is Pakistan: The 1962 war did two significant blows for India. First it made Pakistan believe that with the Chinese help, it will be in apposition to harm India's interest and even to settle Kashmir with military means. Historically, Pakistan was in the league of anti- communist movement aligning with US power through military and economic support and being a member of the CENTO and SEATO. Interestingly despite Pakistan being in the US camp and a member of anti-communist movement, it never had a serious tension with China on the contrary before 1962. Unlike the Soviet Pakistan relations, Pakistan China relation was not much hostile. But after the 1962 war, Pakistan developed a serious relationship with China to contain India and to fulfil her ambition to capture Kashmir. But China despite its closeness and support to Pakistan on international forum and curbing India's clout in the region, it didn't give full support to Pakistan in all the three wars between India and Pakistan, whether its 1965 war, 1971 and during the Kargil war. For India, China -Pakistan bonhomie always influenced its foreign policy towards these countries.

Keywords India-China Relations, Pakistan's Foreign Policy.

Introduction

Pakistan's foreign policy by and larger revolves around India. The nature of its foreign policy determined as a security state where Kashmir would remain a factor to counter Indian position and Pakistan's insecurity after losing three conventional wars with India. Since, it doesn't have the capacity to target India it always employ conventional and non-conventional (proxy, Terrorism) methods in its behaviour. This issue always concerns India while responding to its bilateral relations with China and simultaneously, China always paly a Pakistan card to discomfort Indian to take any hard position whether it's a border issue or the issue of terrorism. The case of Masood Azhar and India's position to designate him a global terror despite G7 minus agrees to follow that has deterred India's relation with China. Similarly, India's own ambition to join Shanghai Corporation Organization or in the Nuclear Supply group member never found any success and this is mainly because there is always a Pakistan factor that overshadows India-China relations.

India's abrogation of article 370 drew an unexpected reaction from China where it didn't play any neutral role and went with Pakistan position. Whether the matter to take it to the UN and therefore now the Pakistan factor would decide what would be the future of China India relations whether its bilateral, regional alliance from BRICS to RIC and would also affect China's offer to India on One Belt One Road Initiative and other overtures like 5G or India's official entry to UNSC or NSG.

India and China is facing a trust deficit from maritime to land borders, from US factor to Dalai Lama and Tibet question and that has helped Pakistan But the biggest question would remain what would be the future of India china relation and what would be role of Pakistan in shaping that significant relations.

Objective of study

The paper would discuss the multiple dimensions to try and established the factors that have shaped India China relation particularly from the Pakistani position or merely the role of Pakistan in Indochina relation from historical to contemporary and future course.

Review of Literature

Various books, magazines, newspaper and online literature have been reviewed for this paper which is discussed through out the paper.

Main Text**2. Trade relations**

Comparative study of China import export to India, China import export to Pakistan rate of growth or decline in trade,

Issue of Chabahar Port

In May 2016, India signed a series of twelve memorandum of understandings which centered upon the Port of Chabahar. The trilateral transit agreement signed by India, Iran and Afghanistan allows Indian goods to reach Afghanistan through Iran. It links ports in the western coast of India to the Chabahar port and covers the road and rail links between Chabahar and the Afghan border.

The bilateral agreement between India and Iran gives India the right to develop two berths of the Chabahar port as agreed in 2015 and allows them to be operated for 10 years by India Ports Global, a joint venture between Jawaharlal Nehru Port Trust and Kandla Port Trust, in partnership with Iran's Aria Banader[1]. India Ports Global has guaranteed handling of 30,000 TEUs by the third year of operations, and aims to eventually handle 250,000 TEUs.

In July 2016, India began shipping US\$150 million worth of rail tracks to Chabahar to develop the port container tracks and build US\$1.6 billion Chabahar–Zahedan railway built by India's Ircon International for which India pledged additional US\$400 million and Iran allocated US\$125 million in December 2016, thus taking the total allocation to US\$575 million (out of US\$1.6 billion needed for the rail route) till the end of 2016. In October 2017, India's first shipment of wheat to Afghanistan was sent through the Chabahar Port. In December 2018, India took over the port's operations.[2]

For Kabul, the Chabahar agreement was a sigh of relief. The Chabahar deal means that Afghanistan is no longer dependent on Pakistan for its transit and trade with India and the rest of the world. It has diversified transit routes options for Kabul, giving an end to the Pakistani transit route's monopoly.

The signing of the Chabahar transit agreement in Tehran has left Pakistan in a quandary. This transit trade agreement, seen with both suspicious and hopeful eyes in Islamabad, has since become a dilemma for Pakistan. It is seen as a potential "security threat" to Pakistan. Though these views can't officially represent governmental policies, they surely shed some light on what Pakistan's power center (the army) might be thinking regarding Chabahar.

The rivalry between Chabahar and Gwadar mostly hinges on two factors. First, analysts posit that the probability of a Chinese and Indian military (especially navy) presence in these ports will increase Sino-Indian rivalry in the Indian Ocean. Second, there is an expectation that Chabahar port will diminish the importance of Gwadar port (the end of CPEC) as a transit hub and route for Central Asian republics and Afghanistan.

Strategically, though Pakistan may give permission to China to use Gwadar militarily, it will definitely be on Pakistani terms. Moreover, Pakistan might also use the port for its own military purposes. However, Iran, for her part, may not agree to allow India to use Chabahar for military purposes. Iran may not want to enter into the Sino-Indian strategic rivalry at a time when Sino-Iranian economic, political, and strategic relations far outweigh Indo-Iranian relations. Bilateral trade between India-Iran is \$14 billion, compared to \$51.8 billion between China and Iran. Moreover, Iran and China agreed in January 2016 to increase bilateral trade to \$600 billion in the next 10 years. Moreover, it was China (along with Russia) that vetoed United Nations Security Council resolutions against Bashar al-Assad's regime in Syria, a strategic ally of Tehran.

Even as China and Pakistan do not share land borders, their military and diplomatic collusion against India—and China's own geopolitical priorities in the region—have brought them together in the Indian state of J&K. With its presence in PoK, China is safeguarding its own political and strategic interests as well as those of Pakistan.

3. Military, Strategic and Security relations

India-China relation has been dominated by India's concern over growing relation between China and Pakistan and China concern over India's engagement in the South China Sea.; Pakistan stand on India China border disputes Constant suspicion between India-China's bi lateral relations; the unsaid proximity of trust between Pakistan and China bi lateral relations.

The close military ties that developed between China and Pakistan during the 1960s have been a major source of friction between India and China. From India's perspective, the Sino-Pakistan military relationship confronts India with a two-front threat, which has materialized several times. New Delhi also believes that China's large-scale assistance to Pakistan's military development is fundamentally anti-Indian. The realities of the situation were clear, from India's point of view: China was arming Pakistan against India. New Delhi also blames the Sino-Pakistan military link for drawing extra regional powers into South Asia where they had no proper role. From New Delhi's perspective, the Sino-Pakistan link has drawn not only China but the Soviet Union and the United States as well into South Asia. In other words, the Sino-Pakistan entente is, in India's opinion, a stimulus to further militarization and great power rivalry in South Asia. Within this context, it is important for our purposes to examine recent developments in Sino-Pakistan military relations[3].

4. Fighting Terrorism and Religious Dimension:

Terrorism is not a new phenomenon; however the intensity of terror attacks has risen higher in the recent years. In the realm of fighting terrorism, China practices a dual policy in connection to India and Pakistan as seen with the recent attacks in Kashmir.

While India's rise as an emerging power remains a main concern for China, the bigger obstacle to Beijing's power projection in South Asia is the presence of Islamic extremists in the Afghanistan-Pakistan (Af-Pak) region and their interaction with the Uyghur Muslims in China's restive province of Xinjiang. Given the deteriorating situation in the Af-Pak region, Beijing fears a percolation of fundamentalist forces into the Xinjiang province via PoK.

Days before the SCO summit in Bishkek in June 2019, Beijing came out in direct support of Islamabad, reiterating that no single country should be targeted for terrorism. The 10-year delay on the Masood Azhar issue showcased China's power politics vis-à-vis India. Besides international pressure, the reversal of China's stand could also be attributed to two other factors: the relentless diplomatic and political heavy-lifting done by the Modi government[4]; and the 2016 surgical strikes and Balakot air raids, which demonstrated India's military assertiveness in the occupied territory and the realization that China's friendship with Pakistan may cost the CPEC[5].

However, China's close ties with JeM and other Pakistan-supported terror outfits—which safeguards its economic and geostrategic interests in PoK is unlikely to end anytime soon[6]. According to reports, some 500,000 Chinese nationals are expected to be living in the Gwadar port city by 2023[7].

China is therefore likely to continue to use the terror groups within the PoK to keep India busy along the LoC and inside the Kashmir Valley. For India, this has also raised serious concerns about China's role in case hostilities break out with Pakistan.[8] The presence of the Chinese PLA within the illegally occupied territories of PoK to its northeast and Aksai Chin to its northwest has raised a security dilemma for India of fighting a two-front war.

The state of J&K is India's natural strategic space and, historically, a diplomatic battleground. India's response to Pakistan's military overtures has been fitting and disciplined, and not directed towards taking the occupied territories back. Over the years, China has sought to limit India's response by entering into territorial agreement with Pakistan, issuing selective criticism of and support to terrorism, and building infrastructure in occupied territory. As India revoked the special constitutional status of J&K and declared Ladakh as a Union Territory[9], China yet again has adopted a pro Pakistan stance by referring to Kashmir as a "disputed territory"[10]. The recent terror attack in Pahalgam and Chinese silence thereafter is a clear indication towards this policy.

For now, Beijing's actions may remain limited to issuing pro Pakistan statements, helping its efforts to internationalise the Kashmir issue and by moving forces along the Ladakh

border in J&K to keep up the pressure on India. It remains to be seen how, in the long run, China's policy would address India's assertion of sovereignty.

5. Locating Pakistan in India-China war/ conflicts:

India-China 1962

While Western nations did not view Chinese actions favourably because of fear of the Chinese and competitiveness, Pakistan, which had had a turbulent relationship with India ever since the Indian partition, improved its relations with China after the war.[11] Prior to the war, Pakistan also shared a disputed boundary with China, and had proposed to India that the two countries adopt a common defence against "northern" enemies (i.e. China), which was rejected by India. China and Pakistan took steps to peacefully negotiate their shared boundaries, beginning on 13 October 1962, and concluding in December of that year.

Pakistan also expressed fear that the huge amounts of western military aid directed to India would allow it to threaten Pakistan's security in future conflicts. Mohammed Ali, External Affairs Minister of Pakistan, declared that massive Western aid to India in the Sino-Indian dispute would be considered an unfriendly act towards Pakistan. As a result, Pakistan made efforts to improve its relations with China. The following year, China and Pakistan peacefully settled disputes on their shared border, and negotiated the China-Pakistan Border Treaty in 1963, as well as trade, commercial, and barter treaties.

On 2 March 1963, Pakistan conceded its northern claim line in Pakistani-controlled Kashmir to China in favor of a more southerly boundary along the Karakoram Range. The border treaty largely set the border along the MacCartney-Macdonald Line. India's military failure against China would embolden Pakistan to initiate the Second Kashmir War with India. It effectively ended in a stalemate as Calvin states that the Sino-Indian War had caused the previously passive government to take a stand on actively modernizing India's military. China offered diplomatic support to Pakistan in this war but did not offer military support. In January 1966, China condemned the Tashkent Agreement between India and Pakistan as a Soviet-US plot in the region. In the Indo-Pakistani War of 1971, Pakistan expected China to provide military support, but it was left alone as India successfully helped the rebels in East Pakistan to found the new nation-state of Bangladesh.

The emergence of the Sino-Pakistan entente simultaneously with the collapse of Sino-Indian relations in 1962-1964 also partly fits this pattern, although in this case the deterioration of China's relations with its initial partner (India) was the cause not the consequence of its movement toward the second partner (Pakistan). There is a somewhat closer fit with the pattern if the system is enlarged to four actors; the deterioration of Sino-Soviet relations speeded the process of China's switching partners on the subcontinent. While previous history does not constitute evidence regarding current international relationships, it is suggestive. Thus, we come back to the question of what impact Sino-Indian rapprochement has had on the Sino-Pakistan entente.

China support to Pakistan in India Pakistan war/conflict

ON September 15, 1965, Mr. B. K. Nehru, India's Ambassador to the United States, told the National Press Club in Washington, D.C.: "What seems impossible to deny is that the Chinese and the Pakistanis are working in the closest possible co-operation to increase the military and economic pressure on India and to encourage internal disorder with a view to weakening, and if possible causing the break-up of, the Indian Union." There has indeed been evidence of Sino-Pakistani co-operation in recent years, though the use of the words "closest possible" might be questioned. Strangely enough the United States, by her arms aid to India since 1962, became at least partly responsible for one of the more successful phases of Chinese Communist diplomacy since the inception of the People's Republic

From 1954 until 1962 Pakistan appeared to be aligned with the anti-Communist nations as a member of both CENTO and SEATO and as a recipient of American military (and economic) aid given specifically with the understanding that its purpose was to help defend Pakistan against "Communist aggression." It cannot be doubted that Pakistan's entry into SEATO and CENTO appeared to be a diplomatic setback for China's policy of surrounding herself with allies, friends or at least neutralist states at the periphery of her national boundaries[12].

Between 1958 and 1962 Sino-Pakistani relations continued to be cautiously friendly and their trade gradually increased. If it is assumed that assumed that Pakistan's foreign policy is determined largely by her feelings of military insecurity vis-d-vis India and by the internal political necessity to placate irredentist sentiment regarding Kashmir, it is not difficult to understand how the policies followed by the Soviet Union and the United States may literally have driven Pakistan into the arms of the Peking regime.

The turning-point in Sino-Pakistani relations which opened the door to the events of August and September 1965 came with the Sino- Indian border war of October 1962. On the one hand India's humiliation at the hands of the Chinese must have encouraged those in Pakistan who felt that a resort to arms might gain Pakistan's objectives in Kashmir. On the other hand Soviet-American military aid to India made it seem less likely that India would accept a negotiated settlement or a plebiscite.

It is thus from 1962 that Pakistan and China increasingly extended their co-operation. Pakistan felt a new respect for China's capabilities and increasingly trusted her, whereas China felt a new contempt for India's pretensions to power and no longer hesitated to offend India by her dealings with Pakistan.

On January 5, 1963, the first Sino-Pakistani Trade Agreement was signed in Karachi, providing for an exchange of Chinese manufactured goods for Pakistani cotton, jute and leather goods. On March 2, 1963, a Boundary Agreement calling for the establishment of a Joint Boundary Demarcation Commission was signed by Pakistan's pro- Chinese Foreign Minister, Z. A. Bhutto, and Chinese Foreign Minister Chen Yi. The Indian Government regarded the agreement as illegal, "since Pakistan has no border with Communist China," and lodged a protest with the Security Council of the UN.

Eventually China's support to Pakistan in 1965 Indo-Pak war further consolidated Pakistan China relations. It also supported Pakistan in 1971 war with India. China is now one of the biggest investors in Pakistan as the great China-Pakistan Economic Corridor (CPEC) is one such example. With the passage of time China-Pakistan relations become sweeter than honey and higher than Himalayas. China has always perceived Pakistan as an important ally which could provide it the much required geostrategic linkages and route access to the Middle East and Persian Gulf. It is also a source for bridging the relations in the Islamic world. China at number of times acknowledged Pakistan's friendship saying "China can give up gold but not its friendship with Pakistan"- President Hu Jintao.

J&K indeed has helped cement a deepening Sino-Pakistan nexus. China and Pakistan have little in common other than a shared interest in containing India. In keeping with the axiom that "my enemy's enemy is my dear friend", the two have forged one of the most enduring partnerships in international diplomacy. Wang earlier declared that China and Pakistan were "as close as lips and teeth". The China-Pakistan axis presents India with the prospect of a two-front war, if India were to enter into conflict with either country.

The Sino-Pakistani ties strengthened further in the 1970s. During the 1971 IndiaPakistan war, China's role was a blend of "tempered support, gentle scolding and steely pragmatism." After Pakistan's defeat, China rushed to help rebuild its military forces.[13] In the 1980s, under the leadership of Deng Xiaoping and in accordance with his push for economic reforms, China sought to improve relations with its neighbours. On the Kashmir issue, Beijing reverted to its old position that it was a matter best left between India and Pakistan[14]. This was also attributed to then Minister of External Affairs Atal Bihari Vajpayee's historic visit to China in 1979[15].

Although Beijing emphasised the Shimla Agreement of 1972 and endorsed UN intervention on the Kashmir issue, it tacitly maintained a pro-Pakistan slant[16]. Later, in May 1998, following India's Pokhran tests, Beijing once again demanded that the Kashmir issue be referred to the UN. While India justified the tests at the international level by referring to China's threat, Beijing termed India's actions as "hegemonic" and blamed India for inciting military tension in South Asia[17]. China also broadened its covert assistance to Pakistan's missile program and modernisation[18]. China's call for international intervention to resolve the Kashmir issue also continued during the Kargil conflict in 1999[19]. However, in 2006, from the World Social 31 32 Forum in Karachi, later in 2009 and again in Dec 2014, the Hurriyat Conference invited China to resolve the Kashmir issue[20]. The Hurriyat hoped that a rising China would bring India and Pakistan together, but it received little positive response. However, Beijing did not completely fail the separatists. In effect questioning India's stance over Kashmir, it began issuing stapled visas to Kashmiris[21]. Beijing continued to rebuff New Delhi even after External Affairs Minister S. M. Krishna visited China in April 2010 and expressed India's sensitivity to the Kashmir issue and the matter of the stapled visas[22]. After all the back-and-forth

on the Kashmir issue, China's true intentions wouldsoon become clearer. The PLA was intent on establishing a foothold in PoK to control the region militarily and diplomatically. Nearly 11,000 Chinese military troops were deployed to PoK, suggesting that Pakistan had given de facto control of the territory to China[23].

Rejecting the media reports about the military presence, Beijing described Gilgit-Baltistan as "Northern Pakistan" and J&K as "India controlled Kashmir"[xxiv]. In doing so, China not only questioned India's locus standi on PoK, it also legitimized Pakistan's claim on the territory.

Infrastructure projects in PoK have helped China consolidate its control over PoK and the strategic Shaksgam Valley, to tie India down in the region. The Chinese road network through Shaksgam, which also connects the KKH with the Tibet-Xinjiang Highway, has led to encirclement of J&K from three sides. While the feeder roads connect crucial military complexes based in China and Pakistan, Gilgit provides the natural cover to military facilities like missile bases and tunnels – enhancing their joint capacity – and making it possible for them to launch pincer movements against India[25].

In 1971, when Pakistan had lost much of its military hardware during the war with India, China came to Pakistan's rescue and made up a major portion of the loss despite the fact that China was then recovering from the impact of Cultural Revolution. In 1970's, Pakistan shared China's perception of the world situation. The Soviet invasion of Czechoslovakia in 1968 had disillusioned the Chinese as well as all other freedom living nations. The Chinese not only denounced the invasion as an act of social imperialism but also felt the need to have rapprochement with the United States.

There was also a change in US attitude towards China. The policy of containment and hostility was overshadowed by threats from the Soviet Union. The Russian effort to gain control of the world's sea lanes was causing concern in Washington as well as in Beijing. By arranging Henry Kissinger's secret trip to Beijing in 1970, Pakistan played an imp role. in the normalization of relations between China and the United States. India and the Soviet Union disliked Pakistan's role in this episode. As a reaction they moved closer to each other and signed the twenty years Treaty of Peace and Friendship which is virtually an alliance for all practical purposes[26].

The first agreement for military assistance of the value of US\$ 120 million was signed by Pakistan and China in July 1966. Within two years China supplied Pakistan 100 T-59 tanks, 80 MIG-19's (F-6) and 10 Ilyshin-28 bombers. By 1970, "the tanks supplied by China already constituted 25 per cent of the entire tank force at Pakistan's disposal. The aircrafts supplied by China constituted 33 per cent of the Pakistani air force's 270 planes, 65 per cent of all interceptors.

Issue of Kashmir:

Changes in China's support for Pakistan on the Kashmir issue are one measure of the impact of Sino-Indian rapprochement on the Sino-Pakistan entente. Improvements in Indian-Chinese relations led to a weakening of China's endorsement of Pakistan on this key issue. Kashmir has been the crux of Indo-Pakistani conflict since 1947. From Pakistan's perspective, the essence of the problem is that India has denied basic human rights to the people of Indian-occupied Kashmir, most importantly the right to self-determination as provided for by United Nations Resolutions of 1948 and 1949 on Kashmir.

India was satisfied with China's position on Kashmir during the 1990 crisis. High-level Indian diplomats in Beijing during the 1990 crisis characterized China's position as relatively balanced. China had not reiterated its old position of support for Pakistan on this issue. Nor had it made any moves to involve the United Nations. China's primary objective was to avoid a conflict between India and Pakistan, they said, and to this end it had encouraged de-escalation and all trends in that direction.

The deterrent support offered by Qin was, however, equivocal: "The Chinese government will never change its policy" officially "supporting the Pakistan Government, people, and armed forces in safeguarding their state sovereignty and territorial integrity, no matter how the international situation changes." [27] This was China's strongest statement of deterrent support for Pakistan during the 1989-1990 Kashmir crisis.

Pakistan saw China as a reliable friend who could be counted on in times of emergency. Subtle nuances of words were less important to them than underlying perceptions and purposes, and these, they were confident, would lead China to continue to support

Pakistan against India. They understood Beijing's need to mince words for the sake of placating India, but remained confident that when push came to shove, China would be there.

Indeed, China has utilized its alliance with Pakistan and the Kashmir conflict to constrain India's emergence as a potential competitor to its own rise in global power dynamics[28]. While such efforts began in 1959—with China and Pakistan building the Karakoram Highway (KKH) passing through PoK followed by the signing of the 1963 46 border agreement, the pushback appears to be culminating into the CPEC.[29]

Issue of Nuclear in China-Pak- India

In a major policy decision made as early as 1982, China identified Pakistan as a worthy client-recipient of atomic know-how. Pakistan's first nuclear-weapon test was carried out by China in May 1990: 'That's why the Pakistanis were so quick to respond to the Indian nuclear tests in 1998. It only took them two weeks and three days.' [30]

In an interview in January 2009, Thomas Reed is a former nuclear-weapon designer at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory and secretary of the air force under presidents Gerald Ford and Jimmy Carter, speculated on the explanation for China's nuclear assistance to Pakistan: 'a balance of power: India was China's enemy and Pakistan was India's enemy'. In turn, Pakistan's Abdul Qadeer Khan Network became a nuclear Walmart for the export of sensitive materials and technology to countries like Iran, Libya and North Korea.

Since 1998, Pakistan has waged sub conventional warfare against India under the subcontinent's nuclear ceiling. State-sponsored cross-border militancy and extremism involving nuclear-armed states is another contemporary reality, as is the fear of nuclear terrorism. The Pulwama attacks on 14th February, 2019 and India's response thereafter made the world realise the need to put pressure on JeM but China oppose the effort on Pakistan's behest.

US has reportedly warned China that assistance to Pakistan in the nuclear field would retard the progress toward a bilateral agreement on nuclear cooperation between US and China. Keeping in view the close ties between Pakistan and China, it has been assumed that China must have provided Pakistan information about the design of nuclear bombs.

6. External factors and in international scenario

The U.S. in 1967 shared this Indian concern about China and its desire to dominate Asia. The Sikkim clashes came even as American troops were fighting in Vietnam, in the midst of Chairman Mao's unfolding Cultural Revolution, and a few months after China had conducted its first hydrogen bomb test. Since a decade before, American administrations had seen India as part of their China strategy – as a potential counter-weight and democratic contrast to communist China. Indian success, therefore, was seen to be in American interest and a way of addressing the China challenge[31].

China has changing as well as enduring interests in South Asia: the former depend largely upon China's policy orientation at particular times and its relations with other countries, while the latter are basically derivatives of the subcontinent's location on China's south-western flank next to the troublesome Tibetan and Sinkiang regions.[32]

The subcontinent is more important to China than it is to either the United States or the Soviet Union. The United States has never been directly vulnerable to any threat from South Asia. Even the co-operation of local states with a great power antagonistic to America does not possess any serious danger to the U.S.[33] The Soviet Union was at one time potentially vulnerable to the air power of a hostile great power based in the subcontinent, but the advent of inter- continental missiles has reduced the value of the air bases in the area for such purposes although the development of nuclear missile submarines has enhanced the potential importance of the Indian Ocean.

Conclusion

China's interests in South Asia are secondary to its key concerns in the world. Its conflict with the Soviet Union, its relations - whether good or bad - with the United States as well as with Japan, and the recovery of Taiwan are all basically more important to Peking than its relations with India, Pakistan or Bangladesh. On the other hand, if only because of proximity China's interests in South Asia (as well as in South-east Asia) are clearly of greater importance than its stake in the Middle East, Africa or Latin America.

(These Chinese concerns are intensified by the memory of the efforts of Great Britain in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, acting through the British Indian Government in New Delhi, to make Tibet a buffer area. The fact that Britain may have been acting in order to fore- stall Russian involvement in the area hardly made the situation more palatable to the Chineses). Ever since the war between India and Pakistan in 1965, the situation in South Asia has remained in a state of flux. After the dismemberment of Pakistan in 1971, India, with Soviet support, could have established its hegemony in the region. But China's political and military support to Islamabad prevented India from realizing her ambitions. China denounced aggression and supported the just struggle of the people of Pakistan to defend their sovereignty and territorial integrity.

The joint communiqué issued at the end of former Prime Minister Bhutto's visit to China in 1972 clearly stated that friendship between Pakistan and China was based on principles that are in accord with the basic interests of the two countries.[34] Pakistan and China are close neighbors. The history of relations between the two countries goes back to the period when merchants, pilgrims, scholars and diplomats travelled on camel or on horseback through the silk route from one country to the other. During the period of colonialism, however, contacts between the people of China and Pakistan were restricted at both official and unofficial levels.

Following the first British aggression against China in 1856 or the Opium War, as it is better known, China's foundation as a state was sapped. As a result, chaos and confusion prevailed in China for a long time.

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